

Multidisciplinary Surgical Research Annals

<https://msra.online/index.php/Journal/about>

Volume 3, Issue 5 (2025)

Prevalence Of Work-Related Musculoskeletal Disorders Among Waiters In Faisalabad

Dr. Arfa Rasool¹, Dr. Fatima Arif², Dr. Iqra Tahir³

Article Details

ABSTRACT

Keywords: Musculoskeletal Disorders, Occupational Disorders, Waiters

Dr. Arfa Rasool

Physiotherapist at The University of Faisalabad, Lecturer at The University of Faisalabad

Email: arfahhh001@gmail.com

Dr. Fatima Arif

Physiotherapist at The University of Faisalabad, Lecturer at The University of Faisalabad

Email: fatimamalik3134@gmail.com,

Dr. Iqra Tahir*

Lecturer at The University of Faisalabad
Email: iqra.tahir@mth.org.pk

fastest growing industry around the globe. Restaurant employees are exposed to a diverse variety of workplace disorders due to the wide range of work tasks and standing in work body positions for lengthy days.

Aims & Objective: The objective of this study is to determine the prevalence of work related musculoskeletal disorders among waiters in Faisalabad.

Methodology: A cross-sectional survey of waiters in Faisalabad was conducted. 260 waiters enrolled from different hotels of Faisalabad. Waiters who met the inclusion criteria were taken in the study. Informed consent was taken from all the participants. Nordic Musculoskeletal questionnaire was distributed to waiters. Waiters were listed their symptoms. Data was entered and analyzed in SPSS V.25.

Results: Frequency tables and bar charts are made to show the prevalence of musculoskeletal symptoms in waiters. According to the results, 26 (10%) of the 260 participants were female, while 234 (90%) participants were male between the ages of 20-40. Results of this study shows that most reported symptoms have been seen in Neck, shoulder and ankle region.

Background: Restaurant industry is the

INTRODUCTION:

Work related musculoskeletal disorders (WMSDs) are a significant cause of occupational impairment and injury across a variety of occupations. WHO estimates that between 50 and 70 % of workers have WMSDs. 6,300 people each die from WMSDs, which affect 317 million people annually.^[1] The restaurant industry is one of the world's fastest-growing in the globe. Restaurants employ many humans while ignoring their health and safety. Workers in the manufacturing sector, who frequently spend their shifts close to conveyor belts, had previously been thought to be the main group at risk for developing work related musculoskeletal problems. However, in recent years, the frequency of work related musculoskeletal problems has increased across all industries, particularly in the hospital, hotel, retail, clerical, financial, and educational sectors.^[2]

Employees in restaurants, cafes, and kitchens are subjected to many risk variables that are closely linked to the initiation of orthopedic illnesses, as determined by a review of the literature and the European Agency for workplace safety and health. Individuals exposed to such risk variables; nearly 33 percent of European employees experience lumbar pain, 20.3% encounter muscle soreness, 11.5% experience upper limb discomforts, and 17.6% encounter lower extremity discomfort.^[3]

WMSD complaints from employees have been trending slightly downward over the past few years but it is significant to note that recent data from the European Agency for safety & health at work (EU-OSHA) study revealed that this health issue still affects more than half of European workers.^[4] From 65 percent in 2010 to 50 percent in 2015, the proportion of the workforce in Italy who report having one or more WMSDs has dramatically dropped. Nonetheless, these conditions make up the majority of occupational diseases in Italy, accounting for 66.7 percent of all recognized occupational diseases in that country in 2018, back pain was most often reported health issue (51.6%, after that 46.7% and 29.3%, respectively).^[5]

Working long hours and standing up for extended periods of time are standard requirements of serving occupations. Many servers don't take breaks too often. There are two causes of infrequent breaks: One of two things happens: either they are not given the chance, or the server does not want to pass up a table and the chance to earn money. In addition to standing, servers are continually moving across the restaurant to help customers or carry out service tasks. Lower back pain and diseases of the lower extremities have been linked to prolonged walking and standing.^[6]

Employees in this food sector are much more probable than other employees to be rejected access to a wide range of public welfare, such as salaried rest periods, recompensed summer break, and paid vacation.^[7] This type of "precarious labor" is related to a number of health difficulties, as well as difficulty gaining access to public and occupational health authorities.

Heavy lifting, repetitive actions, long periods of standing, and other physical demands may be required in the food service industry.^[8] Even though lower extremity abnormalities have long been identified among many restaurant workers, and lower extremity issues have been linked to a sustained static posture among restaurant staff, women food servers are more likely than their male colleagues to develop musculoskeletal difficulties.^[9]

The treatment for musculoskeletal disorders includes several options like pharmacological treatments includes common medications include non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs), muscle relaxants, and corticosteroids to manage pain and inflammation, physical therapy plays a vital role in rehabilitation, helping to improve mobility and strength, lifestyle modifications.^[10] Regular exercise, weight management, and ergonomic adjustments can help alleviate symptoms, alternative therapies techniques such as acupuncture and massage therapy may also provide relief and topical treatments includes pain creams, gels, or patches can be applied directly to painful areas for localized relief.^[11]

Material and methods

This study was cross sectional study. The study was conducted at different hotels of Faisalabad whose names as under: - Baba tikkah kohinoor branch - Tandoori Restaurant - Sariya's sip N bites - Silver spoon continental Restaurant - Forks N Knives - The Dynasty - Nando's. The study was completed

within the time duration of four months after the approval of synopsis. Total sample size = 236 + 24 = 260. Convenient sampling technique was employed.

Eligibility Criteria:

Inclusion Criteria:

- Both genders
- Age between 20-40 years
- Those with more than one year of job experience

Exclusion Criteria:

Individuals with recent fractures, serious systemic illness, a recent history of trauma, polyarthritis, rheumatoid arthritis, or any other arthritic condition, or any psychiatric illness will be excluded. Restaurant employees who had a prior history of a vehicle or other work related accident, physically deformed, or pregnant women will be excluded.

Data Collection Tool:

Waiters were assessed using the Nordic Musculoskeletal Questionnaire (NMQ), which is standardized. Reliability of Nordic Musculoskeletal Questionnaire is excellent with the Cronbach's Alpha value of 0.945.

Data Collection Procedure:

There was a cross sectional survey of Waiters in Faisalabad. Ethical approval from the university was first sought. The hotel manager's approval was obtained before data collection. When a person agrees to participate in the study, their consent was obtained. Nordic questionnaire was given to participants, asking them about their demographics, workplace characteristics, psychosocial data, as well as their musculoskeletal symptoms from the previous year in nine body regions (head/neck, shoulders, elbows, wrists/hands, upper back, low back, hips, and knee. Respondents were listed their symptoms.

Results

Results were analyzed by SPSS version 25 and described with the help of frequency tables, histograms, pie charts, and bar charts.

Descriptive Statistics of Annual and 1Week Prevalence of Work Related Musculoskeletal Disorders

Figure 3 Multiple Bar Chart shows the distribution of annual and 1 week prevalence of work related musculoskeletal disorders of participants in the sample. The above graph shows the distribution of annual and 1 week prevalence of work related musculoskeletal disorders of participants in the sample. Prevalence of neck pain in participants was 26.9% at twelve months and 15.4% at last week. Prevalence of shoulder pain in participants was 19.6% at twelve months and 14.2% at last week. Prevalence of elbow pain in participants was 6.5% at twelve months and 3.8% at last week. Prevalence of wrist pain in participants was 10% at twelve months and 6.9% at last week. Prevalence of upper back pain in participants was 15% at twelve months and 5.8% at last week. Prevalence of lower back pain in participants was 12.7% at twelve months and 8.8% at last week. Prevalence of hip pain in participants was 8.5% annually and 3.1% weekly. Prevalence of knee pain in participants was 6.2% at twelve months and 3.8% at last week. Prevalence of ankle/feet pain in participants was 15.8% at twelve months and 9.6% at last week. Highest prevalence of work related musculoskeletal disorders was found for neck pain having annual prevalence rate of 26.9% and weekly prevalence rate

of 15.4%.

Descriptive Statistics of Impact of Annual Prevalence of Work Related Musculoskeletal Disorders on Activities of Daily Living

Figure 4 Multiple Bar Chart shows the distribution of Impact of Annual prevalence of Work Related Musculoskeletal Disorders on Activities of Daily Living of Participants in the sample. The above graph shows the distribution of impact of annual prevalence of work related musculoskeletal disorders on Activities of Daily Living of participants in the sample. Neck pain prevented 70 (26.9%) participants from carrying out ADLs in last twelve months. Shoulder pain prevented 52 (20%) participants from carrying out ADLs in last twelve months. Upper back pain prevented 39 (15%) participants from carrying out ADLs in last twelve months. Elbow pain prevented 17 (6.5%) participants from carrying out ADLs in last twelve months. Wrist/hand pain prevented 26 (10%) participants from carrying out ADLs in last twelve months. Lower back pain prevented 33 (12.7%) participants from carrying out ADLs in last twelve months. Hip/thigh pain prevented 22 (8.5%) participants from carrying out ADLs in last twelve months. Knee pain prevented 16 (6.2%) participants from carrying out ADLs in last twelve months. Ankle/foot pain prevented 41 (15.8%) participants from carrying out ADLs in last 12 months.

Discussion

A cross sectional study by Yesmin (2013) used a variety of questionnaires to detect the common musculoskeletal conditions linked to the workplace among the 100 restaurant staff members of Dhaka. The study's results revealed that 78% of participants had WRMDs. Neck (22%), spine (38%) and knee (24%) were the body parts with the highest difficulty. Pain was the most prevalent WRMSD symptom (82%), while the spine was the body area most commonly afflicted (38%).^[12] The greatest degree of symptom intensity was moderate (57.7%). Working in the same position for a participant (38%) and carrying a heavy load for a participant (35%) were the most frequent risk factors. The study provided compelling evidence that WRMDs are widespread among restaurant employees. The present study has also shown neck pain to be highly prevalent in the waiters with a prevalence rate of 27%.

However, in the recent study knee pain was not found to be significantly high with the prevalence of only 6% as compared to 24% in Yesmin' study. Likewise, spine pain of upper back and lower back was also found lower in the current study with the prevalence of 15% and 12.7% respectively in comparison to 38% spine pain in the study by Yesmin. Tegenu et al. (2020) conducted a cross sectional study to find out the prevalence of self reported WMSDs and risk variables among 633 restaurant employees in Ethiopia. Data was gathered using a Nordic questionnaire. In the previous 12 months, 81.5% of restaurant

employees had WMSDs. The most severely afflicted body areas were the upper back, lower back, elbow, and wrist. The current study has findings on contrary to above findings as the present study has shown most afflicted body areas to be neck, shoulder and ankle/feet with the prevalence rates of 27%, 19.6% and 15.8%. So, the most painful body areas differ between the two studies.^[13]

Giorgianni et al. (2023) evaluated 500 catering employees in regard to upper limb diseases. The study showed that a variety of catering professionals were impacted by musculoskeletal diseases. The shoulder (48.6%) was the anatomical area most severely impacted. Elbow problems were second in frequency (30.4%), followed by wrist and hand illnesses (22%). These conditions, in particular shoulder, wrist/hand, and daytime and nighttime paresthesias, become more prevalent as people age. The present study has also revealed high shoulder pain prevalence of 19.6%, but this is comparatively lesser than the shoulder prevalence found in study by Giorgianni.^[14]

An investigation was done by Yalew et al (2022) in Ethiopia, with 420 wait staff members to determine the prevalence and contributing variables of work related LBP. Data were gathered using a common Nordic questionnaire. 43.8% participants reported having back pain at some point in the previous year. The present study has found findings in disagreement with study by Yalew by showing less prevalence of LBP (12.7%) in waiters. Lesser prevalence can be due to multiple factors like the mean service years and mean age of the participants in the current study was lesser than those mentioned in most of the articles. The current study has set the range of 20-40 years and minimum one service year for inclusion in the study, so that's why the prevalence figures might be different according to the demographics.

Abdelsalam et al. (2023) performed a survey to ascertain the risk factors related to the frequency of WRMSDs related to working in the kitchens of Egyptian student hostels. There were 128 kitchen employees in the overall sample. A questionnaire for Nordic musculoskeletal disorders was employed. The majority of the culinary staff at the hostel for students reported WRMSDs within the previous 12 months (90.6%). The most affected areas were the lower back (64.8%), knee (46.9%), foot (46.1%), neck (29.7%), and shoulders (23.4%). The present study has somewhat dissimilar findings with study of Abdelsalam as low back, knee and foot pain prevalence was not very higher in the current study. Although neck pain prevalence in both studies is near to each other with 27% in the current study and 29.7% in the above study. All body areas pain was found highly prevalent in study by Abdelsalam as compared to the prevalence found in the recent study. This lower prevalence in the current study may be attributed to the different job nature and working posture of participants in both studies. As the recent study has taken waiters into consideration, while the above study has taken the kitchen staff in the study. So, different job duties can contribute to disproportion in prevalence rate in both studies.^[15]

Wills (2013) conducted a study to examine the possible risks that restaurant servers are frequently subjected to on a typical shift in the Midwest metropolitan area. The upper trunk was the body area that experienced the largest increases in discomfort at the completion of the shift (by 55%). The head (at 45%) and lower spine (at 50%) showed the greatest changes in pain. Furthermore, nearly 70% of the employer carried a tray of meals in front of them, which might result in poor and uncomfortable body posture. Waitresses and wait staff are at risk of Musculoskeletal disorder because of weight transmission, period of standing and moving, and bad posture. The study has demonstrated findings in discrepancy with the current study by having very high prevalence of pain at upper trunk of 55%, while the current study has only found prevalence of 15% at the upper back.

Khutale et al. (2020) undertook a study to investigate the incidence of musculoskeletal dysfunction in 93 food stall employees with more than 5 years of professional experience. Nordic questionnaire was used to assess outcomes. Lumbar discomfort symptoms had the highest percentage of avoiding regular ability to do a job (41%). This was accompanied by knee pain (31%), neck difficulties (20%), shoulder issues (19%), elbow difficulties (19%), forearm problem (8%), upper trunk 6%, and ankle joint discomforts 4% (25). The study has presented findings somewhat congruent to the current study as shoulder pain have nearest

figures of prevalence in both studies with shoulder pain being 19.6% in the current study. However, the major difference between both studies lies in that in Khutale's study lumbar pain was the most common WRMSD, while in the current study neck pain was the most common symptom found. This difference could be due to discrepancy in years of experience. The current study enrolled subjects with condition of at least 1 year experience while Khutale study undertook staff with at least 5 years of experience, so subjects of Khutale's study showed more cumulative WMSDs.^[9]

Strengths

This work is highly pertinent to public health. Thus, the information supports intervention plans to lessen WMSD-related risk factors.

The study had sufficient sample size for data saturation.

Study was multi-center; data was taken from multiple restaurants of the city.

Limitations

The scope of this study is the Pakistani city of Faisalabad. The prevalence was only discovered among waiters.

Self-reporting was the study's most significant limitation, and participants might not have remembered every instance of WMSD, in addition, participants might have overestimated their wmsds in order to avoid having their history of WMSDs stigmatized by their superiors or being viewed negatively as a result, which could prevent promotion or future employment opportunities.

Less female subjects than males were available for this study because more women in Pakistan do not participate in this line of employment because it is stigmatized there. Women are underrepresented in this field for a variety of reasons, including the high physical demands, security concerns, unsafe working conditions, and harmful stereotypes about the industry.

Recommendations

More studies are required to determine the strength or degree of weakening of the body's muscles that experience more pain.

In addition, it is advised to conduct additional investigations using objective assessment and longitudinal study designs to pinpoint the other connected components of WMSDs.

Conclusion

Annual prevalence of WMSDs among waiters was found most prevalent in the neck region, then followed by shoulder, foot and upper back pain. Therefore, as preventive measures to avoid WMSDs, it is advised that waiters emphasize comfortable body posture while doing their duties, engage in physical activity, and take breaks throughout the workday.

Conflict of Interest: None

Funding: No external funding was received.

Use of AI: None

Authors Contributions:

AR, FA and IT contributed to conception and design. AR, FA and IT contributed to data acquisition. AR, FA and IT contributed to data analysis. IT contributed to article drafting and revising it critically for important intellectual content. All authors approved the version of manuscript to be published.

References

- Tegenu H, Gebrehiwot M, Azanaw J, Akalu TY. Self-reported work-related musculoskeletal disorders and associated factors among restaurant workers in Gondar city, Northwest Ethiopia, 2020. *Journal of Environmental and Public Health*. 2021;2021.
- Jeong BY. Cooking processes and occupational accidents in commercial restaurant kitchens. *Safety science*. 2015;80:87-93.
- Lee JW, Lee JJ, Mun HJ, Lee KJ, Kim JJ. The Relationship between Musculoskeletal Symptoms and Work-related Risk Factors in Hotel Workers. *Ann Occup Environ Med*. 2013;25(1):20.
- Juntarawijit C, Juntarawijit Y. Cooking smoke and respiratory symptoms of restaurant workers in Thailand. *BMC pulmonary medicine*. 2017;17(1):1-11.
- Jahangiri M, Eskandari F, Karimi N, Hasanipour S, Shakerian M, Zare A. Self-reported, work-related injuries and illnesses among restaurant workers in Shiraz City, South of Iran. *Annals of global health*. 2019;85(1).
- Bonzini M, Battevi N, Stucchi G, Vitelli N. Epidemiology of illnesses and musculoskeletal disorders in grocery stores and catering. *Giornale Italiano di Medicina del Lavoro ed Ergonomia*. 2014;36(4):226-9.
- Cottica D, Grignani E. Risk assessment for food preparation, cooking and service. *Giornale Italiano di Medicina del Lavoro ed Ergonomia*. 2014;36(4):230-3.
- Graziosi F, Bonfiglioli R, Violante FS. Occupational risks in grocery stores. *Giornale Italiano di Medicina del Lavoro ed Ergonomia*. 2014;36(4):219-25.
- Russo F, Di Tecco C, Fontana L, Adamo G, Papale A, Denaro V, et al. Prevalence of work related musculoskeletal disorders in Italian workers: is there an underestimation of the related occupational risk factors? *BMC Musculoskeletal Disorders*. 2020;21(1):1-16.
- Xu Y-W, Cheng AS, Li-Tsang CW. Prevalence and risk factors of work-related musculoskeletal disorders in the catering industry: a systematic review. *Work*. 2013;44(2):107-16.
- Yesmin K. Prevalence of common work related musculoskeletal disorders among the restaurant workers: Department of Physiotherapy, Bangladesh Health Professions Institute, CRP; 2013.
- Wills AC. Musculoskeletal disorder risk factor assessment in restaurant servers: University of Cincinnati; 2013.
- Lee JW, Lee JJ, Mun HJ, Lee K-J, Kim JJ. The relationship between musculoskeletal symptoms and work-related risk factors in hotel workers. *Annals of occupational and environmental medicine*. 2013;25:1-10.
- Kerckhove N, Lambert C, Corteval A, Pereira B, Eschalier A, Dualé C. Cross-sectional study of prevalence, characterization and impact of chronic pain disorders in workers. *The Journal of Pain*. 2021;22(5):520-32.
- Laperrière È, Messing K, Bourbonnais R. Work activity in food service: The significance of customer relations, tipping practices and gender for preventing musculoskeletal disorders. *Applied ergonomics*. 2017;58:89-101.